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IDENTIFY THE CHALLENGES IN CLOUD COMPUTING & USES OF SELF-DIAGNOSE AND SELF-HEALING SYSTEM AGAINST VARIOUS FAILURES OR DOWNGRADES.

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Abstract:

Cloud computing is a general term for anything that involves delivering hosted services over the Internet. Constructing IT services that use advanced computational power and improved storage capabilities. Cloud computing is in initial stages, with many issues still to be addressed. The objective of this paper is to explore the different issues of cloud computing and uses of self-diagnose and self-healing system against various failures or downgrades and provide a reliable and dependable cloud platform.

Introduction:

Cloud computing is a general term for anything that involves delivering hosted services over the Internet. These services are broadly divided into three categories:

1. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)
2. Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS)
3. Software-as-a-Service (SaaS)
4. Data-as a-Service(DaaS)

Since cloud computing can offer ready access to entirely new business capabilities, less expensive IT resources and unrivaled flexibility for business of every size, it appears to offer significant economic benefits if the risks can offset.

Cloud computing service provider will need a robust, scalable & high performance infrastructure to complete in this emerging market.

The cloud is the resource that incorporate routers, firewalls, gateway, proxy and storage servers. The interaction among these entities needs to occur in a secure fashion. It can be defined as a pool of computer resources that can host a variety of different workload, including batch style backend jobs and interactive user applications. The resource sharing at various level results in various cloud. For this reason, the cloud just like any data center, implements a boundary protection also known as the demilitarized zone (DMZ). The most sensitive information stored behind the DMZ.

The other application runs on cloud is resource priority and application priority. It defines processes and hardware requests in high priority queue to be served first. Application partitioning refers to the usages of one server or storage device for various clients that may have data encrypted differently. The cloud should have defined different user policy for different users on application from the

backend information storage. This may be solved by using virtualization, multiple processors or network adaptors.

Objective of the paper:

Objective of paper is to identify the challenges in Cloud computing & uses of self-diagnose and self-healing system against various failures or downgrades. In information technology, self-healing describes any device or system that has the ability to perceive that it is not operating correctly and, without human intervention, make the necessary adjustments to restore itself to normal operation. Because users of a product may find the cost of servicing it too expensive (in some cases, far more than the cost of the product itself), some product developers are trying to build products that fix themselves. IBM, for example, is working on an autonomic computing initiative that the company defines as providing products that are self-configuring, self-optimizing, and self-protecting as well as self-healing. For all of these characteristics together, IBM uses the term "self-managing."

Fig 1 : Cloud Computing System

Research methodology:

Challenges in Cloud Computing:

Self-healing - In case of application/network/data storage failure, there will always be a backup running without major delay, making the resource switch appear seamless to the user.

Multi-tenancy - The cloud permits multiple clients to use the same hardware at the same time, without knowing them, possibly causing conflicts of interest among customers.

Service-oriented - Cloud allows one client to use multiple applications in creating its own.

Virtualized - Applications are not hardware specific; various programs may run on one machine using virtualization or many machines may run one program.

Linearly scalable - Cloud should handle an increase in data processing linearly, if "n" times more users need a resource, the time to complete the request with "n" more resources should be roughly the same.

Cloud data ownership- In the contract agreements it may state that the CP owns the data stored in the cloud computing environment. The CSP may demand for significant service fees for data to be returned to the enterprise when the cloud computing SLAs terminates.

Analysis:

Self-healing Cloud: Cloud represents a very complex system. As a computer system become increasingly large and complex, their dependability and autonomy play a critical role in supporting

next-generation science, engineering and commercial applications. Clouds offer the automatic resizing of virtualized resources. Cloud scalability is mainly enabled by increasing the number of working nodes and requires dynamic self-configuration in accordance with high-level policies. Cloud computing provides computing services to large pool of users and applications and thus, Clouds are exposed to a number of dangers such as accidental/deliberate faults, virus infection, system failure etc. As a result, cloud often fails, become compromised or perform poorly, therefore becoming unreliable. Consequently, in cloud computing the challenges to design, analyze, evaluate, and improve dependability remains. Clouds are generally massive and complex. In order to cope with their existing complexity and reduce the continued development of their complexity, the difficult but obviously interesting option of endowing clouds with the abilities of self-diagnosis and self-healing present itself. A possible solution may reside in autonomic computing that enables systems to manage themselves without direct human intervention.

Autonomic computing is about shifting the burden of managing systems from people to technologies. The aim of autonomic computing is to develop the systems capabilities of self-managing the distributed computing resources to adapt to unpredictable changes while hiding the system's intrinsic complexity to users. The idea of Autonomic computing is to mimic the autonomic nervous system found in biology.

Professor Martin Rinard, a principal investigator at CSAIL, linked a self-healing cloud network to the human body,

which senses when it's being attacked by a virus and begins self-repair almost immediately. Rinard also leading the work to create a network that will work this way, which at MIT is called the Cloud Intrusion Detection and Repair project.

"Much like the human body has a monitoring system that can detect when everything is running normally, our hypothesis is that a successful attack appears as an anomaly in the normal operating activity of the system," he said in a press statement. "By observing the execution of a 'normal' cloud system we're going to the heart of what we want to preserve about the system, which should hopefully keep the cloud safe from attack."

Conclusion:

To provide a reliable and dependable cloud computing platform, it is necessary to build a self-diagnosis and self-healing system against various failures or downgrades.

Self-healing is the capability to discover, diagnose, and react to system disruptions. The main objective to adding self-healing features is to maximize the availability, survivability, maintainability and reliability of the system. System designed to be self-healing are able to heal themselves at runtime in response to changing environmental or operational circumstances. Clouds are a large pool of easily usable, accessible and volatile virtualized resources. They need to be self-healing because they are so complex, continuously adapting to additions, removals and failures of node/resources. The enormity of how to self-configure

according to a dynamically changing environment is out of the scope.

References:

- [1] Liang-Jie Zhang and QunZhou. "CCOA: Cloud Computing Open Architecture," in Proc. IEEE International Conference on Web Services, 2009, pp. 607-668.
- [2] Geng Lin, David Fu, Jinzy Zhu, Glenn Dasmalchi "Cloud Computing: IT as a Service," presented at IEEE Computer Society conference in Beijing, 2009, pp. 10-13.
- [3] Lee Badger, David Bernstein, "US Government Cloud Computing Technology Roadmap", National Institute of Standards and Technology, Volume I, November 2011
- [4] Kevin Hamlen, Murat Kantarcioglu, Latifur Khan, BhavaniT, "Security issues for Cloud Computing", International Journal of Information Security and Privacy, 4(2), 39-51, April – June 2010.